

Women Empowerment in Contemporary India

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ABSTRACT

This paper focuses on women empowerment in India : Women are the backbone of families and communities. They provide care, support, and nurturing to their families and are essential to the development of children. Women also play a significant role in community building and often take on leadership roles in community organizations. It involves creating an environment where women can participate in society and economy on an equal footing with men, and where their voices are heard and their rights are protected, there are different ways to categorize. Including educational empowerment, economic empowerment, political empowerment, health empowerment and social empowerment. The aims of women's empowerment like that, Empowerment strategies help women to increase their bargaining power, confidence, decision-making autonomy, and give their choices and agency to act on their own and their families behalf with respect to safety. The concept of empowerment is a process that fosters power in people, for use in their own lives, their communities, and in their society, by acting on issues that they define as important. "KUDUMBASHREE WOMEN'S EMPOWERMENT PROJECT " which focused on one of the largest women empowerment projects in India. So women's empowerment aims to create a world where women have the power and freedom to live their lives, without discrimination or limitations based on gender.

Key words: Women Empowerment, Social, Economic, Education, Communities

Introduction

The “term women empowerment” means promoting women’s dignity. So that they are able to make their own choices and influence societal changes. So women empowerment refers to providing the women economical, social and educational rights, without any kind of discrimination based on gender, class, religion or social status. It is an essential prerequisite for the development and progress of a nation.

The government of India has declared 2001 as Women’s Empowerment year. It is a fact that empowerment of women plays a vital role in the development goals of a country and it would create many positive repercussions in the society. Women are the backbone of families and communities. They provide care, support and nurturing to their families and are essential to the development of children. Women also play a significant role in community organizations. It involves creating an environment where women can participate in society and the economy on an equal footing with men and where their voices are heard and their rights are protected.

Under five year plans and also initiatives by the state and central governments, various programmes and schemes have been initiated as a part of empowering women.

As per social scientist there can be five different modes for the upliftment of women, such as, welfare mode, equity mode, anti-poverty mode, efficiency mode and empowerment mode. It seems that amongst these modes, empowerment mode is the well accepted mode for the upliftment of women at present. Anti-poverty mode is also interconnected with women empowerment and starting of various women entrepreneurship are part of this. Amongst various levels of empowerment, economic empowerment makes the women economically independent and self reliable.

Women empowerment is a global issue and discussion on women political rights are at the forefront of many formal and informal campaigns worldwide. The concept of women empowerment was introduced at the international women conference at NAIROBI in 1985. To get women empowerment at the societal level women should be relieved from extreme domestic responsibilities, remove barriers from their daily lives and increase social awareness campaigns through education and mass media programmes.

There are different ways to categorize women's empowerment. That is five common types: Economic Empowerment, Social empowerment, Political empowerment, Educational & Health empowerment. Overall these types of empowerment are interconnected and complementary and empowering women in one area can have positive ripple effects in other areas.

Social Empowerment of Women:-

Social empowerment refers to the ability of women and girls to act individually and collectively to change social relationships and the institutions and discourses that exclude them and keep them in poverty. Not only that It can be defined as promoting women's sense of self-worth, their ability to determine their own choices, and their right to influence social change for themselves and others.

An important aspect of social empowerment is to address prevailing gender norms and roles, in order to improve women's and girls discrimination and position in civil society, economic empowerment is a key factor to improving Sexual and Reproductive Health and Rights (SRHR) of women and girls. It enhances their ability to have a voice in decision making processes like marriage and pregnancy.

This type of empowerment refers to women's ability to participate fully in social and cultural life free from discrimination and violence. It includes access to education, healthcare and legal services, as well as the ability to exercise their rights and freedoms.

Social empowerment is perhaps one of the most prominent forms of women's empowerment. It gives rise to women's social relationships and places in the social structure, giving them more opportunity outside of the household activity. Social empowerment helps women in fighting against discrimination, allowing them to fight against race, ethnicities, religions, gender and sexualities.

An example of social empowerment initiatives is the provision of quality education and skill development programs to marginalized communities, enabling them to acquire knowledge and skills that can improve their employment prospects and overall well being. Social empowerment aims to improve the social status and well-being of individuals or marginalized groups within society. It involves promoting social inclusion, equal rights and

opportunities, as well as challenging social norms and prejudices that perpetuate discrimination and exclusion.

The government of Kerala has adopted various strategies to enhance the status of women and empower them to address the negative social and economic impacts. Because women empowerment will lead to an improvement of the socio-economic conditions of the society in a number of ways.

Kerala is one of the few Indian states that has backed the trend and created a model of development. That is more inclusive of women. The concept of women's empowerment as part of a broader goal of gender equality has become a key focus for countries around the world. It is widely recognized that economic and social development cannot be achieved to its full potential without ensuring gender equality. While there is no country in the world where women enjoy exactly the same rights as men, Kerala has made significant progress in this area. .

Kerala launched the Kudumbasree programme in 1998 by the LDF Govt with an aim to empower women and eradicate poverty. After 25 years of its launch, Kudumbasree has been a huge success today which focused on one of the largest women empowerment projects in India.

Kudumbasree supports women in a number of ways through training, entrepreneurship support, education and more. Kudumbasree, a community organization of Neighbourhood Groups (NHGs) of women in Kerala, has been recognized as an effective strategy for the empowerment of women in rural as well as urban areas, bringing women together from all spheres of life to fight for their rights or for empowerment. 'Kudumbasree', which means prosperity (shree) of the family (Kudumbam) is the name of the women oriented, community based, state poverty eradication mission of Govt of Kerala.

Across Kerala, Kudumbasree covers 991 Panchayats and 87 municipalities.152 Block Panchayats,14 District Panchayats. Through this network women have the freedom to demand, and to receive money without red tape. In fact, banks volunteer to lend money to Ayalkoottam. Like the Dhanalakshmi Bank, which plans to lend Rs. 300 crores to Kudumbasree Ayalkoottam alone, testifying the credibility and investor confidence the women have inspired under the Kudumbasree network.

In 2010 Kerala became the first state in India to reserve 50 percent of their seats for women in local self government. According to the recognition, about 50 percent of the women who are currently involved in local govt. have attained leadership skills from their involvement with the Kudumbasree organization. The women's network functions with a three tier structure. Neighbourhood Groups (NHGs) at the lowest level, Area Development Societies (ADS) at the middle level, and Community Development Societies (CDS) at the top level.

Economic Empowerment of women

This type of empowerment refers to women's ability to participate in economic activities on an equal basis with men. It includes access to education, training employment, and entrepreneurship opportunities, as well as fair wages, equal pay and access to credit and financial services. Women go beyond social responsibility and can have a positive impact on the economy. Women owned firms result in increased jobs, and yield substantial sales and receipts. Women economic empowerment is the transformative process that helps women and girls move from limited power, voice, and choice at home and in the economy to having the skills, resources and opportunities needed to compete equitably in markets as well as the agency to control and benefit from economics.

- Historically economic development leads to gains in gender equality and GDP per capita
- Increasing women's participation in the economy leads to gains at home, at work and in society at large.
- When women have economic power, their families benefit too.
- The capacity of both women and men to participate in, contribute to and benefit from economic growth is essential to transforming the lives of poor and marginalized women and girls.

Through our global research partnership and support foreign research institutes in Kenya and India, we are helping to build an evidence base on effective approaches to women's empowerment, which can inform policy design.

In India knowledge evidence generated about the positive effects of the federated structure of women's self help groups have spurred the formation of similar structures within the govts. Poverty alleviation projects, the National Rural Livelihood Mission, we are experimenting with replicating this approach in Nigeria and Uganda, and in India we aim to expand and deepen our efforts, including through private – sector value chains and digital platforms.

Women empowerment will be real and effective only when they are endorsed with income and prosperity so that they may stand on their facts and build up their identity in the society. Kudumbasree is fundamentally a women's organization. It took birth in the specific developmental and political content of Kerala State. Empowerment of women involves many things, economic opportunity, social equality and personal rights, Kudumbasree plays a vital role in enhancing the financial status of the less privileged women in the state through its thrift and credit societies. These societies facilitate them to save and provide them with effective and easy credit. The savings of the women are pooled together and given out as loans to the most deserving.

Kerala has 1200 local self governing bodies, 941 Grama Panchayats, 152 Block Panchayath, 87 Municipalities, 6 Corporations and 14 district corporations. 100 micro units of Kudumbasree from Kollam, Kottayam etc. These districts of Kerala region are selected by random sampling method and members of the selected units are the respondents. That is, the Kudumbasree programme could bring about radical change in the lives of the poor sections of the society.

Educational Empowerment of women

Pandit Jawaharlal Nehru once said that “if you educate a man an individual, however if you educate a woman you educate a whole family”. Women empowered means mother India empowered.

Education is a milestone of women empowerment because it enables them to respond to the challenges, to confront their traditional role and change their life. Education of women is the most powerful tool to charge their position in society. Not only that, it can help them to gain knowledge, skill and confidence that can help them to improve their lives and the lives of their families and communities. The concept of women empowerment is recent. The first

year of the new millennium 2001 was declared as “Women Empowerment Year”. Education of women leads to a better family and ultimately an ideal society to a progressive nation. A progressive nation is one where all the people of the country in respect of sex, religion, caste, creed and color are economically, socially, culturally, politically and through all thoughts are independent. Empowering women through education, finance and jobs is one major step to allowing women in India to lead. But the most impressive step towards positive change has been made through the governing practices and politics in the region.

Educational status of women in India

As per the 2011 census, the total literacy rate in India stands at 74 percent and the rate of literacy among women is 65.46 percent. The percentage of female literacy in the country was 54.16 percent. Women education in India has been a major preoccupation of both the government and civil society as educated women can play a very important role in the development of the country. Women empowerment is a global issue and discussion on women's political rights are at the forefront of many formal and informal campaigns worldwide. The concept of women empowerment was introduced at the international women conference at NAIROBI in 1985. The constitutional directive to provide free and compulsory education for all children up to the age of 14 years has remained unfulfilled till now.

Government scheme for improvement in Girls Education

The expansion of education among girls/women has been an integral part of educational policies and programmes. The Ministry of Human Resource Development has taken a number of initiatives for expansion of girls school and higher education, details of which are as under.

School Education

- Kasturba Gandhi Balika Vidyalaya – this scheme was launched in July, 2004, to provide education to girls at primary level. It is primarily for the underprivileged and rural areas where literacy level for girls are very low. The schools that are set up have 100% reservation, 75% backward class and 25% for BPL (Below poverty line) girls.

- Beti Bachao, Beti Padhao – This is the newly announced scheme of the Govt. of India for enhancing girls education in India.
- UDAAN – Giving Wings to Girl students – The scheme is dedicated to the development of girl child education, so as to promote the admission of girl students. The aim is to address the teaching gap between school education and engineering entrance examinations. It seeks to enhance the enrolment of girl students in prestigious technical education institutions through incentives and academic support.
- Mahila Samakhya – Mahila Samakhya (ms) is an ongoing scheme for women's empowerment that was initiated in 1989 to translate the goals of the National Policy on education into a concrete programme for the education and empowerment of women in rural areas, particularly those from socially and economically marginalized groups.
- Saakshar Bharat – The National literacy mission was recast with its new variant, Saakshar Bharat launched in 2009. It aims to accelerate adult education, especially for women (in the age group of 15 years and above) who have no access to formal education, targeting female literacy as a critical instrument for women's empowerment.
- Mid-Day Meal Scheme – The gender gap in school participation tends to narrow, as the Mid-Day Meal Scheme helps erode the barriers that prevent girls from going to school. The Mid-Day meal Scheme also provides a useful source of employment for women and helps liberate working women from the burden of cooking at home during the day. In these and other ways, women and girl children have a special stake in the Mid-Day-Meal Scheme.

Higher Education

- Higher education of women through Open and Distance Learning (ODL) Mode.
- Post school diploma (Polytechnics etc.) : To provide financial assistance for the construction of women's hostels in the existing polytechnics.
- The UGC has launched a number of schemes to encourage the enrolment and promotion of girls in Higher Education.
- Day Care centers in universities and colleges
- Post graduate Indira Gandhi Scholarship for single girl child for pursuing

- Higher and Technical education construction of women's Hostels for Colleges.
- Development of Women's studies in Universities and colleges
- Scheme of capacity building of women managers in Higher Education
- Post-Doctoral fellowship for women.

Now Indian Govt. has taken several steps for women upliftment in India. Some of them are :

(1) Formation of women commission

It was formed in India 1992 January 31st, as a statutory body. It consists of the chairman and other members. First Chairman Jayanthi Patnaik, and the present Chairman Rekha Sharma.

On these basis all states have formed their own women commission. Which is known as the state women commission. In Kerala : It formed in 1996 during the period of A.K. Antony (Chief Minister of Kerala).

(2) Introduced Gender budgeting : That is meant by women development Oriented budget, in which more funds earned marked their developments and introduced different yojanas and schemes. Through gender budgeting, the Govt. of India tries to reduce the gap between men and women. Gender budgeting in India started in 2005.

(3) RTE Act (Right to Education Act)

It was introduced in 2009 in Indian Parliament and came into effect on 1st April 2010, through which Education became free and compulsory.

Universalisation of elementary education, for all children from 6 to 14. It is annexed in Article 21(A) of Indian constitution. One of the main aim is increase education for Girl child and abolish of child labour. Likewise 25% of total seats should be reserved for economically weaker section and society disadvantage children including girl child.

(4) Women Reservation Bill

Women Reservation Bill introduced in Indian Parliament through 108th amendment of Indian constitution. It proposes that 1/3 of all seats in Lok Sabha and all state legislative

assemblies be reserved for women. The Rajyasabha passed the Bill but Lick Sabha has not yet passed. Rajya Sabha passed women reservation Bill on March 9th 2010, during the period of Manmohan Singh. But Lok Sabha has not yet passed. Due to severe opposition from the leaders of Mulayang Sing Yadav, Lalu Prasad Yadav, Mamatha Banerji, Sarath Yadav etc.

But at the same time Govt. of India reserved 33% of total seats for women in Local Self Govt. in India, through 73rd and 74th amendment of Indian constitution. During the period of former Prime Minister P.B. Narasimharao. On the basis of this bill Kerala reserved 50% of total seats for the women in Local Self Govt.s. UNO had directed the reservation of women in the Indian parliament But in the case of women reservation India shared only 149th position in the world out of 193 member countries in UN.

Equal Remuneration Act:

It was implemented in 1976, which says that equal pay for equal work for men and women. That is under MGNREGA (Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Govt. Act) 'equal pay for equal work'.

Special Education Facility for Girl Child

In India and all states a lot of education schemes for the development of girl child are introduced. Example, Beti Bachao Beti Padhao, Sukanya Samridhi Scheme. In Tamilnadu Periyar EVR Nagammai free education scheme has been implemented in this state from 1989 onwards.

Formation of Ministry and Child development :

It was formed under MHRD, it gives special attention for welfare of women and children.

Poverty Alleviation Programme

With Five year plan (1974-79) Government of India given to special attention for poverty alleviation programme because the main aim of Government was Poverty and unemployment to abolished. All these schemes women get much more attention.

Overall women's education is essential for achieving gender equality and empowering women to realize their full potential .By investing in girls education, we can create a more just equitable world for all.

Conclusion

To conclude this paper, it may be said that women in the modern hi-tech society which is moving very fast under the shadow of population explosion, conflicts and corruption can mold personality of the adolescent and youth in a proper direction and perspective, provided the women are themselves in power. The educational, social and economical and other policies for women empowerment should be implemented in reality for empowering women in the world.

Today there is a grand awakening among women. Given the opportunity, they will deliver the results. Empowerment of women is absolutely necessary in strengthening her personality. The need of the hour is to provide an opportunity in a conclusive atmosphere free from gender difference. The need for awareness, motivation to be an active member of the society and courage for the faults of male counterparts are great challenges today. When we remove the barriers that women and girls face and provide opportunities for them to fulfill their aspirations, we unleash a powerful and urgently needed engine of progress – women's talent, energy and creativity to help build economics and solve problems.

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